

Ideal Gas Entropy and Macrostates Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that the notion of linking dE to TdS follows from $dE = E d \ln(E)$ and the further notion that $E = \frac{3}{2}NkT$, which in turn follows from $PV = NkT$. In particular, one then has: $dE = T k d \ln(E^{\text{power } 3N/2})$ where $E = \text{power } 3N/2$ is proportional to the volume of a sphere in $3N$ momentum space. The extra constant disappears under the derivative. As a result, the notion of dE being linked to $T dS$ where S is entropy arises readily. For the volume, the number of states is $V^{\text{power } N}$ which is then linked to $PV = NkT$. (We ignore the issue of identical particles at present and a gamma function which appears (1), but discuss these in the note.)

The purpose of this note is to show how Shannon's entropy is equivalent to the entropy as the \ln of the number of states (with two dividing factors (1)). We argue that this follows directly from the use of reaction balance to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution: $p(e) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$. Reaction balance does not seem to be linked a priori to any notion of states, but one may write for the ideal gas case: $E = T \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)/C(T))$ and from this show that if $S = -k \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$, the $dE = T dS$ (V constant). In the above $dE = E d \ln(E)$, we showed that this is also linked to $dE = TdS$ (volume constant) and so Shannon's entropy equals $-kT d \ln(\text{Number of states})$.

Energy and Entropy from Part 1

In Part 1, we argued that: $dE = E d \ln(E)$ with $E = \frac{3}{2} NkT$. Then:

$$dE = T d \ln(E^{\text{power } 3N/2}) \quad ((2)) \text{ for } V \text{ constant}$$

$E^{\text{power } 3N/2}$ is proportional to the volume of a sphere in momentum space with $3N$ degrees of freedom.

We note that $E = \sum_i e_i$ and that $E^{\text{power } 3N/2}$ leads to e_i product terms with $3N/2$ factors. One may permute these $3N/2$ ways (where N is very large) and still have the same state if particles are indistinguishable. As a result, it seems that one should divide:

$$E^{\text{power } 3N/2} / (3N/2)! \quad ((3))$$

The number of states is linked to

$$\ln(E^{\text{power } 3N/2} / (3N/2)!) \quad ((4))$$

for the energy part and

$$\ln(V^{\text{power } N} / N!) \quad ((5))$$

For the spatial part with again identical product terms due to permutations divided out (i.e. $(3N/2)!$ and $(N)!$).

One then has: $dE = T dS - P dV$ ((6))

with S being $-\ln(\text{number of phase space states with redundant permutations divide out} / h^{\text{power } 3N})$ ((7))

We now try to show that this definition of entropy is equivalent to Shannon's entropy in the ideal gas case.

Shannon's Entropy and Reaction Balance

Both Shannon's entropy form

$$S = -k \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((7))$$

and reaction balance:

$$E_i + E_j = E_k + E_l \text{ with } p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l) \quad ((8))$$

do not seem to be linked to the counting of states.

$$((8)) \text{ leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution: } p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{where } C(T) = \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((10)).$$

$$\text{One may write: } E = T \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)/C(T)) \quad ((11))$$

We now try to establish dE (noting that it is ultimately due to a change in T because N and V are kept constant here.)

$$\text{First: } E = T (S - \ln(C)) \text{ where } S = -\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((12))$$

$$dE = dT E/T + d + T dS - T d \ln(C) \quad ((13))$$

$$d \ln(C) = E/TT \text{ so}$$

$$dE = T dS = -\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((14))$$

$$\text{We found above, however, that: } dE = T d \ln(E^{\text{power } 3N/2}) \quad ((15))$$

$$\text{and generalized to } S = k \ln(\text{number of states in phase space} / h^{\text{power } 3N}) \quad ((16))$$

Thus:

$$S = k \ln(\text{number of states in phase space}/h^{\text{power } 3N}) = - \sum \text{over } i \, p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((17))$$

This is the Shannon's entropy equivalence which follows from using reaction balance as a way of solving for $p(e_i)$ explicitly and then trying to link this notion to the \ln of the number of states.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we showed in Part 1 that using $dE = E d \ln(E)$ with $E = 3/2 N kT$, one may readily associate $dE = T d \ln(E^{\text{power } 3N/2})$ and then consider $dE = T dS$ (volume constant) with S being the number of states in momentum space. One may generalize this to consider phase space and include $V^{\text{power } N}$. Here we note that if one may reduce identical permuted values of e_i products and $V^{\text{power } N}$ product terms by dividing: $E^{\text{power } 3N/2} * V^{\text{power } N}$ by $N! * (3N/2) !$. One may then use Stirling's approximation to first order for N extremely large.

In this note, we use reaction balance to solve for $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$. There is no notion of states in phase space, but one may write: $E = - T \sum \text{over } i \, p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)/C(T))$ and then find dE . We show that this leads to the Shannon's entropy form $-\sum \text{over } i \, p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ which must be identical to $S = k \ln(\text{states in phase space with identical permutations divided out}/ h^{\text{power } 3N})$. Thus, there is the Shannon's entropy form and the $\ln(\text{states})$ form for entropy for an ideal gase.

References

- 1 Grimus, W. On the 100th anniversary of the Sackur-Tetrode Equation (2013)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1112.3748>